

Relativistic Energy and Momentum Representing Quantum Information in Space and Time?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 24, 2025

In (1), it seems that it is suggested that a particle, such as one in an oscillator, is coupled to a field with frequency ω and that quantum results appear because the particle is in resonance with these fixed frequencies in the field. Here we suggest that the periodicity of quantum mechanics follows from two results for a free particle. The first is the well-known $x=vt$ (where v is velocity) and the second is an expression from special relativity: $p = \frac{E}{c} = \frac{E}{v}$ (obtained for a particle with mass). This equation suggests that if one considers $\frac{E}{c}$ to represent a velocity term (in terms of units) (it equals c for $v=c$), then $\frac{E}{c}$ and $\frac{E}{v}$ represent gradations (or pieces of information) in space and time. In other words, it is the consideration of E and p as not simply representing dynamic variables, but also gradations or information in space and time that leads to the periodicity of quantum mechanics, we argue. Thus, this argument holds even for a photon and one does not necessarily need to have a separate field in resonance with a particle.

The main point we make is that the Lorentz transformation for either a photon or rest mass particle may be derived strictly as a spacetime transformation. In the photon case, $x/t=c$ and $x'/t'=c$ and in the rest mass case, $x'/t'=v$. By applying this space-time transformation to pc and E , one is suggesting that even though these are not running variables (but numbers), they are linked to the form $x=vt$, but as representing gradations. These gradations lead to the periodicity of free particle quantum mechanics.

Derivation of the Lorentz Transformation for a Particle with Rest Mass

The Lorentz transformation may be obtained for a particle with rest mass if one assumes two frames:

- (A) A particle with rest mass m_0 , is at rest ($v=0$, $p=0$, $KE=0$) at $x=0$ at t
- (B) This particle is seen from a frame moving with $-v$ such that $x'/t' = v$

Given (A) and (B), it seems that this idea immediately excludes photons and only pertains to x, t transformations. In particular, one may write;

$$\begin{aligned} |A| & \quad g(v) \frac{v}{b} \quad |x=0| \quad ((1)) \quad \text{Here } b \text{ is a constant with units of velocity} \\ |B| & \quad g(v) \quad |t=b| \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Then: } x' = g(v) v t \quad \text{and } t' = g(v) t \quad ((2))$$

Thus; $x'/t' = v$ which is the constraint one imposes in the first place. As a result, one has a transformation pertaining to space and time at this point and nothing more.

If x is not 0, then:

$$x'/(bt') = (Ax+gvt) / (Bx + gtb) \quad \text{leading to a possible solution of; } A = g(v) \text{ and } B=g(v) v/b \quad ((3))$$

The question we ask is whether ((1)) may possibly apply to momentum as well. As we have noted before, $x=vt$ means that v turns on x like a switch because $v=0$ turns off x , so to speak and $v=0$ also turns off p . In that sense, there is a link between p and x . If one considers energy as kinetic energy, then $KE=0$ in the rest frame, but has a value in the moving frame, but t is always present in the rest frame. This leads to a problem with KE as full energy. If one proposes that m_0 is proportional to a full energy in the rest frame, then $(p \cdot \text{constant}_1, m_0 \cdot \text{constant}_2)$ could be used to form a vector which transforms according to (1), we argue.

At first, this might seem like the transformation ((1)), which is essentially a space-time transformation in the manner developed above is now applied to p and m_0 , but we argue that this means that the key constraint equation; $x'/t'=v$ must now apply to:

$$P \cdot \text{constant}_1 / E \cdot \text{constant}_2 = v \quad ((3))$$

In fact, the exact expression is: $p / (E/b) = v \quad ((4))$ where b is a constant with units of velocity

$$\text{For the sake of argument, if } b=c \text{ and } v=c, \text{ then } pc = E \quad ((5))$$

What happens in the case that $v \neq c$, even if $b = c$?

We have argued that b is a constant with units of velocity. This constant seems to hold in all frames just as c , the speed of light seems to hold in all frames because it is linked with parameters in electromagnetic theory which presumably don't change when viewed from a moving frame. The transformation ((1)) is explicitly derived for space-time (i.e. x',t') and is based on a rest frame and $x'/t'=v$ which do not apply to a photon. One would at first glance exclude photons from the transformation, even if $b=c$ and a photon has an E and p as well.

The question becomes: If E and p transform according to ((1)), why does nature distinguish between photon energy/momentum and rest mass momentum/energy? Clearly the rest mass cannot hold for a photon and neither does $x'/t'=v$ unless $v=c$.

One may, however, consider the transformation ((1)) with the two photonic constraints:

$$x/t=c \text{ and } x'/t' = c \quad ((6))$$

Assuming $x/t=c$ and using ((1))

$$x'/(ct') = (x+ vt) / (vx/c + tc) = (c+v) / (v+c) = 1 \quad ((7))$$

The transformation ((1)) maintains ((6)) for a photon if $b=c$. Thus, it should hold for p and E of a photon as well and one obtains:

$$E=pc \text{ from the invariant } E^2 = pc^2 + m_0^2 c^4 \text{ for } m_0=0 \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is consistent with the gradations in space-time.

As a result, one may derive the Lorentz transformation in two space-time ways, one for a particle with rest mass and the other for a photon. The photon approach imposes $x/t=c$ and $x'/t'=c$, while the rest mass approach imposes $x'/t'=v$. The same transformation holds for both cases. Furthermore, it applies to pc, E for both.

Implications of E and p Transforming in the Same Manner as x', ct'

The point we wish to make is that creating a transformation ((1)) based on the space-time relation $x'/t'=v$ (or the photon conditions) and applying it to p, E means that one has a velocity type equation ((4)), but with E and p as variables. Now E and p are numbers, not running variables and so one may interpret this them as:

$$\Delta x = \text{constant} / p \text{ and } \Delta t = \text{constant} / E \quad ((9))$$

In other words, p and E are dynamical variables, but may serve as informational gradations in space and time. These uniform gradations of fixed size do not exist in Newtonian mechanics and seem to be part of the nature of E and p which are involved in interactions.

As we have argued in previous notes, space-time seems to be uniform, i.e. have no preferred regions, but the constant valued gradations ((6)) seem to break this notion. We have argued that a uniform distribution should hold within the gradations, but should also indicate the gradations. This leads to:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((10))$$

((10)) is the unnormalized quantum free particle wavefunction. It tracks information in space through its phase px as well indicating that there exists spatial \hbar/p (and temporal \hbar/E linked with $\exp(-iEt)$) gradations.

We argue that this notion of E and p being linked with space-time ultimately arises because the same transformation ((1)) applies to both x, ct and pc, E . We, in fact, derived ((1)) only as a space-time transformation, but argued that v is a switch which turns on both x (as a running variable) and p as a constant, i.e. for $v=0, p=0$ and $x=\text{constant}$ point. T is a running variable regardless and a particle with rest mass m_0 has a constant not affected by v . This same principle holds for a photon because its energy in one frame exists regardless of v . $-v$ is the velocity of the moving frame and changes the perceived energy of the photon. A photon has a fixed p and a running x in a given frame, but that is because c is not 0. One may have $v=0$ in the given frame and a second frame moving with $-v$. Then, v is again a switch which changes the value of p for the photon.

We stress that ((1)) seems to be derived using space-time arguments, whether these be for a photon or particle with rest mass. Using ((1)) for E and pc seem to imply that these interaction variables are also ultimately linked with motion in space-time which is something one would not have thought considering Newtonian mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the key idea of free particle quantum mechanics is that E and p are linked with space-time through $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$. E and p are interaction variables in Newtonian mechanics and are not linked with $x=vt$ for a free particle. We have argued that one may consider a space-time transformation ((1)) for either a particle with rest mass or a photon. The constraint $x'/t'=v$ holds for the particle with rest mass and $x'/t'=c$, $x/t=c$ for a photon. Interestingly, the same transformation holds for both. One would at first not consider applying this space-time transformation to pc and E , but we have argued that these variables are linked to v in a similar manner as x and t . In particular, for a particle with rest mass, $x=0$ and $p=0$ until a v changes both based on existing variables in the rest frame, namely t and m_0 . This suggests a dynamic spacetime type relation for E and p , namely; $p/(E/cc) = v$ or $p(cc/v) = E$. Here cc/v has units of a velocity suggesting that $constant/p$ is like a length gradation and $constant/E$, like a time gradation. For $v=c$, one has $c = cc/c$. We thus suggest that by using the Lorentz transformation ((1)) as a spacetime transformation and applying it to E and p which are constants, one forces E and p to become linked to gradations in space-time. It is this which leads to the periodicity of $\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx)$ of free particle quantum mechanics, we argue.

References

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